

Web Audio interface to access High Frequency radio for Hermes telecommunication system

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe HERMES, High-frequency Emergency and Rural Multimedia Exchange System, a new telecommunication system to share data between remote stations through High Frequency (HF) Radio. HERMES is being built to be used by isolated communities, in emergency or catastrophic situations or in any communication that needs to be private and secure, since it works outside the internet. It has a custom hardware that consists in a digital radio controlled by an Arduino, and a computer that runs a web server that can be accessible through a web interface by a cellphone or laptop. With Hermes is possible to send public messages between stations and also emails to and from the internet for large distances, such as hundreds of kilometers using HF (shortwave) radio. The new version of the system includes a web audio interface that allows access to the radio, to listen and send audio, using a cellphone or a laptop as controller. Here we give a background about the project's development and describe some of the technical solutions employed, as well point to possible new directions on it's development.

1. INTRODUCTION

HERMES is a technology system for connecting remote locations through high frequency radio. HF radio is being used to connect remote locations without access to telecommunication infrastructure as allows communication through large distance without necessity of heavy physical infrastructure. Although big tech companies are already providing satellite access to the internet to remote locations, their costs are prohibitive to several isolated communities that live primarily on extractivism practices. Rhizomatica, that is developing the system,¹ is an organization devoted to develop technologies for alternative communication systems, for "people around the world facing oppressive regimes, the threat of

¹<https://www.rhizomatica.org/>

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Web Audio Conference WAC-2022, December 6–8, 2022, Cannes, France.

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natural disaster, or the reality of living in a place deemed too poor or isolated to connect", working in providing technology development, policy and regulatory advocacy, capacity building and implementation, research and knowledge production. Most of the technologies developed by them are in open source formats.

For isolated communities, the lack of basic infrastructure is the main issue to provide communication, since the long distances require too much physical material to provide electricity and telephone wires. Amateur radio is largely used on these places to connect, but they require the communication to be synchronous, and traditionally don't allow data communication, such as text messages, images or files.

In case of natural disasters, such as earthquakes and hurricanes, amateur radio has also been proved to be one of the most reliable source of communication as pointed by [7] and [16]. As Mentioned by Diniz [8], HF telecommunication systems have much interest of military institutions, but there are few projects to allow civilian communication of data through radio.

In several isolated communities, the lack of communication makes an impact on economic, social and political activities. The economic elites that dominate synchronous communication media has power to controls information that are transmitted through radio, for example, as mention Bofo in his study about development communication in Africa [14]. In his words, it's difficult for the population to "participate and making decisions on political socio-economic and cultural development issues". Sanches-Taberno [20] also identify a tendency of centralization of communication media, that "force to the opinion of a few in detriment of the freedom of expression of independent actors and new communication media".

Is noticeable a correspondence between share of the population with internet access and economic development, as shown in figure 1, a map that shows the share of population with access to the internet by country. Around half of this population that has no access to internet also has no access to healthcare, education, housing or work and many of them are in areas of conflict and migration [3]. As pointed by Munõz, the tech companies have no interest on provide access to them, as they are not consumers for their products.

Is noted that for communities on the Amazon rain-forest, for example, amateur radio is one of the main communication medium, and it's important for emergency communi-

Share of the population using the internet, 2019

All individuals who have used the Internet in the last 3 months are counted as Internet users. The Internet can be used via a computer, mobile phone, personal digital assistant, gaming device, digital TV etc.

Source: International Telecommunication Union (via World Bank)

OurWorldInData.org/technology-adoption/ • CC BY

Figure 1: Share of individuals Using Internet by country.

cation in cases of territory protection, economic and health issues [18]. But amateur radio communication is a point to point communication that needs to be synchronous, i.e., rely of someone to be actively watching the channel to answer a call. Also, by being point to point, it is restricted to the persons that are talking and listening, and they need to communicate to the rest of the community by other medium, such as speaking.

2. BACKGROUNDS

Backgrounds of the Hermes system has its origins on the Fonias Juruá Project, started in 2014 [6] with collaboration of researchers from universities from São Paulo and Brasília, and people from Upper Juruá River Reserve, a territory for natural conservancy on the Amazonia rain-forest, in the state of Acre, to provide HF network to isolated communities. Besides HF radio communication, the project made an experiment to transmit data between computers, using analogical radio signal to transmit an image over a 50Km distance [5].

Since 2013, Rhizomatica, together with REDES A.C was supporting an autonomous cellular telephone system based on open source technologies in Oaxaca[1], Mexico. That region is naturally formed by mountains and valleys and has very poor coverage for commercial cellphone technologies. There was already a strong community organization on the region, where 85% of the territory is self-governed by indigenous norms, which helped to implement and maintain it's independent system. Also, the region has an estimated number of more than 100 community radios, that transmit information pertinent to their context.

At that time, Rhizomatica was already providing support

for HF radio infrastructure in the region [3]. And there was a need for data communication, but also a concerns about consequences to be on the internet in the actual scenario of censorship, surveillance and control, so it started this experience with autonomous communication system for data sharing. Together with a researcher from the "Fonias Juruá" Project, Rafael Diniz, Rhizomatica started to develop the Hermes project to data communication over large distances over HF radio, that is specially suited for the region geography.

Although these regions of isolated communities have poor or none coverage for cellphone communication also, it was noted that there was a lot of smartphones, that was being used as video cameras, alarm clocks, music players, flashlights and other [3]. So the proposal was to use the smartphone as an interface to send data trough radio, using local WiFi connection.

In 2018, Rhizomatica was awarded the first prize on the Mozilla Foundation competition for innovative wireless technologies to "connect the unconnected"² with a demonstration of this previous version of the system, in Oaxaca region. With this grant, it started to focus on developing the current version, that has it's own customized hardware and new user interface.

This system is being requested mostly by indigenous communities to help in protecting their territories, to provide public information and also to promote economic activities between them. Once installed, the system can work without any monthly payment or control, which provides a safe (all data transfers are encrypted over the air) and long term

²<https://wirelesschallenge.mozilla.org/#about>

alternative communication medium for these people.

Currently, we have installed six stations for the Achuar amazonian community in Ecuador, and are building four more for the Kanindé indigenous reserve on Roraima, in Brazilian Amazon Forest. They are also developing a custom modem for the next version of the system, that may allow multiple communication between stations at the same time, and to enhance the velocity of data transmission over the air.

On the beginning of march of 2022, the first Hermes boxes were delivered to the Achuar Community on the Ecuador. Eight boxes were installed in total, and a workshop with the community has been done to train the system administrators and the user community. On May 2022, four boxes will be delivered to the Kanindé Reserve in Brazilian Amazon, and they should include the new interface that will allow the Ham Radio access trough the smartphone, using web audio technology.

3. HERMES SYSTEM

HERMES combines a set of technologies in order to provide telecommunications services over the HF frequency band. Among these technologies are an affordable HF transceiver, a high-performance software-defined modem, the Unix-to-Unix Communication Protocol (UUCP) and a set of user services available over a local WiFi network.

The HERMES WiFi network, provided by each station, ensures access to a web interface that is accessible by computers and mobile phones browsers, and allows user management and system configuration, besides a public message system that can be exchanged between stations. Users can also create custom email accounts, to provide private communication and also connection to other email users on the internet.

3.1 Hardware

Hermes box consists of a custom made hardware, consisting of a computer with WiFi network, an Arduino, a digital HF radio (current version uses UBITX v6) and custom made circuits to provide protection to the system.

It has connection inputs for power (12 V DC), HF Antenna (PL-259), external WiFi antenna, Ethernet Port for connection to external switch or router, ground and fuse replacement on the back. On the front panel, 4 LED's to indicate system status, antenna, connected status and Transmission of data.

An HF antenna tuned to the desired operating frequency must be connected to the equipment. For short and medium range communications (up to about 800 km), a quarter wavelength dipole installed in inverted V configuration is recommended as an affordable option.

The equipment is supposed to work with off the grid electrical systems, such as batteries fed by solar charge or diesel generators, but can also be attached to electricity with an external power supply.

Inside the custom-made box there is a Ubitx ³ radio, a motherboard with Debian bulls-eye release, and an Arduino, that connects the computer to the radio and controls the box's LEDs. There is also a custom made circuit for radio protection and coolers. To protect the integrity of the system against misapplication, we don't offer external audio

³<https://www.hfsignals.com/index.php/ubitx-v6/>

Figure 2: Hermes Stations for Achuar Community, from top to bottom: Central Station installed on Puyo; Hermes Box installed in remote community; User accessing web interface through the smartphone. Pictures: Peter Bloom, 2020

Figure 3: Schematics of basic elements of Hermes System.

connectors nor peripheral entrances such as USB or HDMI. For the same reason, the original radio interface was removed, so the only control is from the Web GUI provided through WiFi.

3.2 Hermes software

Hermes currently is based on different software system to function: *rhizo-uwardop*, that uses VARA or ARDOP modem to provide UUCP integration with HF, *uucomp*, to compress mail transport over the network, *ublox6 firmware and user-land tools* for arduino and command line tools for the radio control, *station-api*, custom developed php API to provide services for the user interface and *hermes-gui*, the web user interface. The source codes⁴ are provided as free software.

The system employs UUCP protocol [17] [11] to transmit files over the network, since it is most suitable for unstable communication provided by our current radio modem. Stations communicate with each other through a scheduling configured on a central station that is connected to the internet and acts as gateway, forwarding the Hermes email messages to and from the internet. The central station calls to the other stations in a round robin way, and orchestrate the message transmission between them at times that are set by the users. In emergency cases, Hermes stations can also make direct communication between them, out of schedule and without the necessity of the gateway station, as the stations keep in listening mode when they are not actively transmitting.

3.3 Modem

To increase the efficiency and resilience of data transmission under the limited bandwidth, several state-of-the-art technologies are being used in the under-development HERMES software-defined modem, such as the Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM), Bit-interleaved Coded Modulation (BICM), and the Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) Forward Error-correction Codes (FEC).

The OFDM allows for a low symbol rate while maintaining the overall data rate by dividing the bandwidth into orthogonal sub-carriers eliminating the need for a frequency guard.

The BI part of the BICM allows for higher protection against Rayleigh fading and pulse noise. The modulation allows for the deployment of high modulation order when

⁴Source codes and documentation of the Hermes systems can be found at: <https://github.com/digitalHERMES>

Figure 4: First Sketch for HERMES web interface diagram.

the channel conditions are favorable and a higher data rate is needed. The coding stage provides the main data protection against electromagnetic noise and interference by deploying LDPC codes [4].

The LDPC codes were originally introduced by [10] and due to their near-Shannon-limit performance, they became the *de facto* FEC in modern telecommunication systems [15].

The LDPC codes decoding complexity is the main challenge in their implementation as the FEC codes of the Hermes software-defined modem as decoding the LDPC code in software and real-time is not possible for most data rates and decoding algorithms [13]. Therefore, the Hermes software-defined modem is deploying the Gradient Bit Flipping (GBF) decoding algorithm that can be easily implemented in software while still providing a decoding performance that is superior to the classical low-complexity decoding algorithms such as the Bit Flipping Algorithm (BFA) and the Weighted Bit Flipping (WBF) Algorithm [12].

The C++ based decoder and OFDM modulator/demodulator would allow for easy portability to low-cost, low-power PCs such as the RaspberryPi. Therefore, allowing for a battery-operated PC to decode an LDPC message without a specialized chip.

3.4 User Interface

Although the boxes can be accessed and configured by ssh through a VPN, they are built to be kept in areas with no internet access. For that Hermes system relies mostly on the web interface for its operation and configuration.

Once a user enters the Hermes WiFi network and open the browser, its directed to Hermes web interface (Figure 5) that allows several actions such as user creation, webmail access, public message system and system administration. The current version has translations for English, Portuguese and Spanish, and was built in Angular⁵, using a custom made PHP API.

3.4.1 User Management

⁵<https://angular.io/start>

Figure 5: Hermes Web Interface - landing page.

Everyone with access to the Hermes network can create an e-mail user to maintain private communication, these e-mails are forwarded to and from the internet by the central station, allowing data communication over the internet. There are regular users, than can use the system to communicate, and also administrator users, that have access to admin features such as radio and message configuration, message deletion, force transmission.

Some of HERMES features can have customized permissions, such as the public message system, that can be configured to receive messages from everyone, registered users or only administrators. File attachments can also be configured the same way.

3.4.2 Email Integration

Personal messages on Hermes system should be exchanged by e-mail. Everyone with access to the network can create an e-mail account for that domain name. We offer access by web mail, using a RoundCube⁶ mail server and also provides download links for Deltachat⁷, that is a mail client with a messenger look and feel. The e-mails are processed to ensure high compression on attachments, using state of art compression algorithms.

3.4.3 Public Messages

Besides e-mail communication, the system provides also a public message system, that works like a Bulletin Board System (BBS), the system's administrators can configure which kind of users can compose this type of message, that can be accessed by the whole community. These messages

⁶<https://roundcube.net/>

⁷<https://delta.chat/en/>

Figure 6: Hermes Web Interface - Radio Configuration interface.

can also have attached media, such as audio, media or other types of files. Public messages, that can be read by everyone with access to the network can be an efficient way to share useful information and news between and to their own communities.

Because the propagation by radio is very slow, Hermes employs heavy, state of art compression mechanisms for both image and audio, to keep file sizes as low as it is possible to transmit over the air. At this version, the final size limit for attachments is 20KB, and the total transmission queue (for both e-mails and public messages) must not be bigger than 70KB.

3.4.4 Radio Configuration

Hermes web GUI provides tools for testing and for radio configuration (Figure 6), such as changing frequency, transmission mode, SWR protection level, turn on Ptt, test tone generator and controlling of other radio parameters.

3.5 Web Audio to Ham radio

The new version of Hermes system, that is being delivered at this moment, also implements an interface to use traditional amateur radio through the smartphone, using web audio and web sockets to send data to the computer sound card, and then to the radio, allowing multi-user access to the radio and to use the cellphone as microphone and headphones for using their station as a regular amateur radio, in case that synchronous communication is needed or in emergency cases.

For that we are customizing an implementation of the "Universal HamRadio Remote HTML 5 interface"⁸, that

⁸https://github.com/F4HTB/Universal_HamRadio

employs a python server and an HTML5 interface to remote controlling of a digital radio using traditional Tx and Rx commands. The python tornado server employs websockets to write and listen on the linux ALSA. There is also another websocket to control the radio commands and configurations, such as frequency, PTT, etc.

3.6 Message transmission

Our current technology only allows one connection at the time, and it's centralized by a gateway station. If the gateway station fails, the transmission needs to be forced by the local stations to propagate the messages, but e-mails to outside internet will not be delivered. We are working to implement a system that other machines could become central nodes also if connected to internet, so in case of losing the central, other box could behave like one.

Since the communication by radio is unidirectional, as radio cannot transmit and receive simultaneously, all communications are coordinated by the central station, and happens one after another. The messages and e-mails go to a queue to be transmitted on the gateway schedule times. If there are more messages that can be transmitted during that time, messages can be postponed. Because of this limitations, an admin can cancel jobs that are still in the queue.

4. FIELD TESTS

HERMES system prototypes were tested on a test bed with stations installed in three cities: Brasília/DF, Belo Horizonte/MG and Hortolândia/SP. Most of the tests happened between Brasília and Belo Horizonte, and Belo Horizonte and Hortolândia. The straight line distance between Brasília and Belo Horizonte is 620 km, while Belo Horizonte and Hortolândia straight line distance is 470 km. All the stations are equipped with simple dipole installed as inverted V, tuned to the 40m amateur radio band. In our internal tests, between Belo Horizonte and Hortolândia, the modem reached more than 1000 bps in an average propagation condition (0db of SNR in the receiver). A 10Kb message, which is the typical size of an email with a picture takes about 4 minutes to be exchanged. In poor propagation conditions, this time can go up to 10 minutes. The adaptive modem starts the communication with slower speeds, but if propagation is good, it gears up and automatically and increases the speed, and on the other hand, if propagation deteriorates, the modem reduces the speed, increasing the signal robustness.

5. CURRENT ISSUES

The whole Hermes system is being developed by a small team of programmers and was built from scratch. So all the mechanisms of the API and interface are being developed simultaneously with the hardware development and manufacturing by a team of seven people.

Manufacturing of the Hermes box is a major issue, since is being built manually with hardware parts coming from other countries. For that we are looking for potential partners that could help to produce boxes in bigger scale.

Software still needs further development, to improve usability, such as form validations on the front-end, handling errors and other new features. We also want to develop our

Remote_HTML5

own code for accessing Ham Radio, for better integration with the API resources and interface.

Integration with other systems developed by the open source community its also something possible, such as of media archive system for traditional communities Baobaxia[19], that also works outside the internet, or automated surveillance systems for territory protection.

More general issues are related to permission to use the HF spectrum that may vary depending on the country legislation, and this requires political agency and social pressure for better regulation.

5.1 Conclusions

Free communication media is an idea that moved the first inventors of the internet [2], as it was born free and open source, but now it's becoming everyday more centralized and under surveillance. The open source community its discussing for a long time about the necessity of creating new free forms of communication, and transmitting data over radio has being proposed for that for a long time, among other perspectives, such as free satellites, independent cellphone networks etc [9].

Although Hermes is not designed to replace the internet nor other communication media, it provides an alternative for data communication trough the air. This could help on health and education issues, security, improvement of commerce and general organization issues for people that are outside the internet. Even for connected people, it could also be useful in cases of emergency, for example in a potential block or damage of internet infrastructure. Different usage of this technology could be useful for monitoring sensors and alarms in isolated locations, such as weather stations and other remote facilities.

By allowing to access Ham Radio from the user's cellphones, it's could be also useful for the Amateur radio community, to improve accessibility for their own practices. We still don't know how this first communities will make use and it's important to get users feedback for both technical development but also conceptual design of all the systems involved. Only with the usage and with time we will have a better pictures of the consequences of this new media for their communal activities and social economy.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors would like to thanks Rhizomatica Telecommunications, the Achuar Conferedaratio, Kanindé Community, Deltachat, Mozilla Foundation, and all the individuals and institutions involved in supporting, building, using and testing the system.

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APPENDIX

A. LIST OF HERMES SERVICES

Network services:

- Web server
- SMTP (Simple Mail Transfer Protocol)
- SMTPS (Secure Simple Mail Transfer Protocol), with SSL support
- IMAP
- RoundCube Webmail server

Network services:

- BBS P2P public messaging capability (over UUCP);
- E-mail user administration;
- UUCP queue management;
- HF radio transceiver management tools;
- Customized permissions for users send multimedia messages;
- Page for radio service tasks (like test tone generation and PTT control);
- A network information page;
- DeltaChat client downloads for Android, MacOS, Windows and Linux.

Other network services:

- SSH Secure Shell - for special system administration: port 22
- VPN - Virtual Private Network client ready for remote access
- ISPCONFIG admin web interface
- mariaDB, the Database server for storing messages and users on station-api and ISPconfig
- E-mail services with transports connected to UUCP Postfix, dovecot, spamassin, postgrey, amavis, clamav (hold) and ISPconfig as a manager
- iwatch: handles inbox HMP folder and triggers UUCP spool compression
- hostapd: sets the wireless interface into Access Point mode
- dnsmasq: provides a domain name server and aliases
- uucp: accessible via network with credential
- VNC: Virtual X session environment with VARA monitor